

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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Annotation: Any child who demonstrates a normal level of development is able to learn any language they encounter in the environment in which they live and has the potential to communicate with others. any child without a pathological defect can learn two, three or more languages. However, a child's level of proficiency in each language varies from one language to another, depending on the need to use that language and the environment. Many studies today show that the success of foreign language teaching in childhood is achieved if it is carried out with appropriate methods and approaches. However, such success can only be achieved through the use of language teaching methods and teaching materials that are appropriate to the students' level of learning.

Keywords: foreign language, transition methods, competence, ICT, multimedia, media, phonetics, lexicon, grammar.

As in our country, in systems where a foreign language is limited only by the scope of the lesson, the time and speed at which the language is taught is crucial. 5-7 years to acquire knowledge of listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary acquisition and to apply all these skills in a foreign language from an academic point of view correctly and flawlessly There should be a curriculum that provides for regular and effective classes. From this point of view, a week of foreign language classes in grades 2, 3 and 4 is not enough. Language teaching, which is a natural means of both written and oral communication, requires continuity. A 7-8 year old elementary school student may not be able to master a foreign language system that is only available for 4-5 hours a week and cannot be used in their own environment.

Effective learning of foreign languages, easier assimilation of new vocabulary has always been a topical issue, although it has been studied by many scholars. In today's era of globalization, it is natural to take such an approach to this issue. Often, the organization of bilingual education in the study of a foreign language allows for in-depth study of several foreign languages. encountered. Modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and Internet resources play an important role in solving these problems. ICT 1 and Internet resources can be a factor in increasing students' interest in learning, including the effectiveness of learning, including motivation to learn a language. The ability of teachers to create their own e-learning resources through ICT is important in the development of this field.

It is important to note that if a student is fluent in his / her native language and has the ability to follow the rules, his / her existing linguistic experience will help him / her to learn another foreign language. Helps to master grammatical concepts and terms of the language faster. In this way, it is easier to learn another language by learning the similarities and differences between languages. Comparison of linguistic phenomena at the phonetic, lexical, grammatical level provides material that enriches the field of linguistics. Therefore, comparative analysis between languages is important. This not only helps to master the new material in a foreign language, but also to make it more interesting for students. If a student knows the rules and basic concepts of one language, he is confident that he can learn another language. As a person acquires linguistic knowledge, it is as if he or she is discovering scientific discoveries in his or her mind, which motivates him or her to learn more and more.

In this regard, it is important for the teacher to explain the differences and similarities between the languages in the course of the lesson, especially the use of modern information technology tools, electronic resources to make the lesson easier for students to master and Comparative study of lexical and grammatical phenomena of the language provides a great opportunity to perform various exercises. In addition, the growing number of language learning sites in recent years has not only facilitated the process of mastering a complex and tedious language learning - lexical units, but

also with the enjoyment of entertaining game exercises using these resources. In a sense, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that it provides spiritual nourishment, as well as the opportunity to relax. Examples of such electronic dictionaries are www.lingualeo.ru and others. However, each word in such a dictionary can be re-presented to the user many times, which means that when learning it, the correct spelling of the word, the lexical pronunciation by the representatives of the language-speaking people will be remembered. firmly located and helps to overcome difficulties in translating texts.

It is known that modern youth are representatives of the culture of their time, they are more influenced by visual images, in other words, the material can be read more quickly and effectively using audiovisual means, rather than in the traditional way. 'will be adjusted. For example, the topic of a language-speaking country is usually taught in a traditional way, using a text consisting of several pictures. This method did not always give the expected result. In modern teaching methods, Power Point presentations, films, slide shows, as well as virtual tours and websites help to solve this problem with their authenticity, visuality and interactivity. Using ICT tools will be more effective in showing videos in a foreign language during the teaching process. Students enjoy watching and completing assignments with interest.

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